

FUTURE SPECIALISTS – SPIRITUAL AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS – A NEED FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF OUR INDEPENDENT COUNTRY

Zaripova Gulbahor Kamilovna

Bukhara State University, Faculty of Information Technology,
Associate Professor of the Department of Information Systems and Digital
Technologies, Doctor of Pedagogical PhD.

E-mail: dersuzala1972@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In the article entitled “Future specialists - spiritual and professional education of secondary school students - the need for the development of our independent country,” the author describes the practical implementation of educational reforms in our country, which serves to educate, first of all, an independently thinking person, in conditions of independence, in as a result of which the highest goal of our independent society was scientifically and practically explained in this article, and in this global direction in our country the need arose to educate a person who is perfect in all respects intellectually, morally, aesthetically, spiritually and physically.

Keywords: Law “On Education”, “National Personnel Training Program”, developed democracies, future specialists, experience of developed countries, great goal, ideal person, independent society, highest goal, internal (biological) and external environmental education, general secondary students schools, spiritual and moral education, dialogues, conversations, ideology.

The education reform being implemented in our country has found its scientific, theoretical, socio-economic, political and legal expression in the Law “On Education” and the “National Personnel Training Program”. The goal of the “National Personnel Training Program” is a radical reform of the education sector, freeing it from ideological views and prejudices of the past, creating a national system for training highly qualified personnel that meets the high moral and ethical requirements at the level of developed democratic countries” [1].

The implementation of this task requires a radical change in the educational process, its content, form and methods, and the educational process in educational institutions. When organizing the educational process in educational institutions, it is extremely important to pay special attention to educational work, to train highly qualified specialists in them, and also to form them as individuals with high moral

qualities. The work carried out in this direction has received international recognition and has begun to bring first results. As a result, the economic and social development of our republic has accelerated.

However, taking into account the factors of its future development, it is necessary to adapt the training of specialists to world standards, transform them into their own specialties and socio-political knowledge. In new historical conditions, it is impossible to solve complex economic, political, spiritual and ethical problems facing society without self-improvement. Because when solving them, it is important that the mind, intellect, and social activity of a person feel their responsibility to the people and the nation. The construction of an independent state with a change in a person's worldview and his consciousness is a dialectically interdependent process.

Analyzing the processes of people's mastery of science, education and ideas, we become witnesses to the fact that any idea, decision, law is laid down in people's minds, actions, behavior and is implemented in practical activities through their cognitive and spiritual world. When a person acquires ideas, decisions and laws and turns them into his spiritual property, it becomes possible to change society and people. Therefore, in the face of our independent state, raising a new, free, independent, independent-minded person has become a matter of life and death. This social necessity requires reforming the entire system of education and training on a new, ideological basis. After gaining independence, our country is developing on the basis of its own socio-economic and political development, that is, the "Uzbek model" laid down by I. Karimov from a scientific, theoretical and practical point of view. We can say that this model, in a certain sense, has justified itself in life and has earned the right to life. Proof of this in life is the evolutionary development of all spheres of public life in our country.

The experience of many developed countries of the world has shown that the economic, political and spiritual development of the state is inextricably linked with the system of education and training. Because the main object of the education and training system is the knowledge of a person's personality, his spiritual and moral character, and professional maturity. Therefore, it is impossible to implement a single issue in the country without human participation, level and qualifications of personnel.

In conditions of independence, it has become socially important that education, first of all, serves to educate an independently thinking individual. At the same time, at its center, not only the interests of the state were placed in the foreground, but, above all, serving the needs of the individual. In the new historical conditions, education and personnel training are becoming the driving force behind the country's development. It became clear that "...education reform is today's most pressing problem, which will decide our fate tomorrow" [2]. "To put it bluntly," says Karimov, "the achievement of our great goals, our noble intentions, the renewal of our society, the progress and

prospects of our lives, the results of our plans, the fate of our reforms, the success of our plans - all this, first of all, with the problem of training highly qualified, conscious specialists who meet the requirements of the time, we all understand that they are closely related” [3].

We see that a person’s education, the level of education, is important not only for the current development of society, but also for the future. Thus, in conditions of national independence, the formation of high moral qualities in future specialists has become an important and integral task of the educational process. Because the treatment of a person under administrative command control, mainly through external administrative influence, deprived him of his will, desire and independent decision-making, turned him into a slave of administrative oppression, turned him into a robot who automatically obeys instructions and orders. In conditions of market relations, a specialist is free from administrative pressure, his creative, independent thinking, his general spirituality, pure morality and social activity, along with high professional training, have become a requirement of life. It became clear that a person’s decision-making based on the situation in the production process depends on the inseparable nature of his personal qualities, human and professional culture.

It is these qualities that encourage a specialist to be creative and, in turn, through their profession make a huge contribution to the economic, social and cultural development of society. These qualities require specialists to be ready, through their conscious development and self-awareness, to contribute to the interests of the people, the Motherland as an individual and as a professional. This need includes the formation of regulatory mechanisms based on an objective assessment and control of the future specialist over his work, his human dignity and personal pride, while the educational process in a secondary school should play a key role. The reason for this approach to the formation of a specialist is that the inner spiritual world of a person turns norms of behavior into an internal motive, and the motive plays the role of a guide. In this case, the student’s activity in the educational process increases, he realizes his development as an individual, deeply mastering his profession in its entirety, under the influence of an internally recognized motive.

Based on this, in modern conditions, when training specialists in secondary schools, an important place is occupied not only by professional, but also by the formation of his personal qualities in mutual proportionality. “The fate of development is decided by spiritually mature people. Technical knowledge and the ability to master complex technology must be combined with spiritual integrity and independent thinking. High intelligence and spiritual potential are the two wings of an enlightened person,” says I. Karimov [4, 13]. From the opinion of I. Karimov, it is clear that in the conditions of national independence, the attitude towards the training of specialists has

also changed, based on the need for social development. In conditions of independence, we must return to our history, culture, customs and traditions, and this should be the main criterion for training specialists. Because in our national heritage, special attention was paid to educating the morality of the child before giving him knowledge. To get a good harvest from a certain crop, the land was first cultivated, and after preparing it, seeds were thrown into it. In the same way, before imparting knowledge to a person, it is important to educate him morally. Therefore, at present, the training of specialists in higher educational institutions, along with professional training, is a determining factor in nurturing high human qualities and spirituality.

Education and upbringing must be carried out in a complex manner. Education is important because it guides a person to understand his essence, to be good in his professional activities, to do good to people. Therefore, Islam Karimov said: “The future begins today. If we do not pay attention to the issue of education now, the future will be lost. We do not regret anything from education. Spiritual and moral purification, faith, honesty, piety, honor, kindness and similar real human qualities do not come by themselves. No wonder he emphasized that education is the basis of everything [2, 53].

It is important for our republic to gain independence and boldly follow the unique model of socio-economic and political development, that is, scientifically and practically substantiated by I. Karimov: “This is a matter of life, death, salvation, destruction, happiness or disaster.” These words of the great enlightener were equally important and relevant for our people at the beginning of our century, they are just as important and relevant for us today” [2, 39]. In conditions of independence, the education of a new, free, independent-minded person has become a pressing issue for our independent state. “That is why, from the first years of independence,” says I. Karimov, “there was an urgent need to reform the spheres of education, science and vocational training throughout the country.” Without this, it would be impossible to begin to change any area of our society” [2, 41]. The fate and effectiveness of reforms depend primarily on the level of personnel, how well they meet the requirements of time and development. Our country emphasizes that the future life and fate of our country are closely connected with the solution of these problems, and the education of every thinking person and the level of his education are considered an important factor accelerating the development of society. In the conditions of a new independent society, an approach to personality and its education on a new methodological basis has become a historical necessity. This problem was scientifically solved by the 1st President of Uzbekistan in his book “The Perfect Generation – the Basis of the Development of Uzbekistan” and a number of other works.

At the present stage of development of our country, an important task of education is the formation of a national idea among young people and, on this basis, a national

ideology. Because “...the national idea must, first of all, help us in our noble task of educating our younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, loyalty to the country, instilling in their hearts the virtues of philanthropy and philanthropy” [2, 41].

The idea of independence, like any innovation, makes its way in the conditions of a very complex socio-political, economic, and ideological struggle. At the same time, not only the solution of market relations on a new economic basis, but also the struggle for the formation of the consciousness and ideology of a new person continues in its forms and methods. It is no secret that, firstly, the communist ideology, which has long occupied a strong place in the minds and thoughts of people, has not been completely eliminated and greatly hinders the development of our society. Much theoretical and practical work to restore national values, as well as a sharp change in attitude towards religion, which is an important form of national values, was reflected in progress on the path to independence. These things manifest themselves in our society not only in the form of struggle between old and new, but also through religion, which is an effective form of human emotions, thoughts and beliefs, the winners of our independence strive to fight the idea of national independence. These processes require a completely new organization of goals and objectives of the approach to the training of specialists, moral and ideological aspects of the formation of their personality, their education in general, based on the idea of independence.

In this case, the main task of education is to form future specialists as individuals with strong faith and independent thinking. I. Karimov: “In such a situation, if a person does not have his own independent opinion, stable beliefs, life and national values by which he lives, a formed worldview and a strong will, it is impossible for him to withstand the pressure of various ideologies, their pressure, sometimes openly, sometimes secretly. This can be observed in the example of many events that occur in everyday life,” he rightly states [2, 33].

As mentioned above, the most powerful tool that constantly controls a person’s behavior, aspirations, interests, needs, behavior and morality is a person’s trust, beliefs and worldview, formed on the basis of his ideology. On their basis, the meaning and purpose of life, hopes for the future, oneself and others are determined, the perception of society, feelings such as “Who am I”, “Who will I become” and “How will I achieve this” are formed at every age. They, in turn, find expression in the life ideals of young people.

The essence, structure and components of the activity of an ideal person are formed on the basis of action, need, interest, motive and orientation. It should be noted that the ideal determines the social essence of all human behavior, is focused on the future and always guides his behavior, morally.

The highest goal of our independent society is to educate a person who is perfect in all aspects intellectually, morally, aesthetically, spiritually and physically. After all, the socio-political, economic, legal and ideological development of society cannot be imagined without the improvement of the individual. That is why, as I. Karimov noted on this occasion: “... the reform of the education sector is becoming today the most pressing problem that will decide our fate tomorrow” [3, 51]. From these thoughts it is clear that it is impossible to solve the complex problems facing society without improving the person himself. Because when solving them, it is important that the mind, intellect, and social activity of a person feel responsible to the people, the nation. Our first President I. Karimov explained that building an independent society by changing human consciousness is an interdependent dialectical process: “...Education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is a factor determining the level of consciousness and its development. Therefore, it is impossible to change consciousness without changing the education system. Without changing our way of thinking, we will not be able to build a free and prosperous society. As we see, all these issues are closely related to each other, like a chain” [2, 40].

Solving this complex problem requires a radical improvement in the quality of education and training of specialists in higher education institutions. Instilling in young people a sense of responsibility to the Motherland and the people requires educating them not for the present, but for the future: “... Achieving our goals, building a new democratic society, the fate of reforms, what intellectual powers we have, what cultural and professional level our youth have reached what ideals it depends on faith, how spiritually enriched it is,” says I. Karimov [4, 31].

Human development is physical, mental, spiritual and moral improvement, which is a qualitative and quantitative change in characteristics formed under the influence of his birth and living conditions. The decisive role of education in this is that it brings the factors affecting a person into line with the requirements of society. This helps them understand the social essence of the issues that society poses to young people.

That is why I. Karimov: “Only a country and a nation can achieve a great future if they can educate professionally competent and enthusiastic people, true patriots of their country, enrich them with the great spiritual heritage of a great national culture, and enjoy the masterpieces of world science and culture. We must not forget that this is possible,” he emphasizes [5, 362]. This poses the task of educating future specialists to develop positive personal qualities so that they have a deeper knowledge of their profession. Therefore, a complete solution to this problem is included in the state program. As noted in the “National Personnel Training Program”: “Effective organizational and pedagogical forms and means based on the rich national cultural and historical traditions, customs and universal values of the people will be developed

and put into practice.” “The education of the individual and its comprehensive development is a priority” [3, 54]. Therefore, today spiritual and moral education and further intensification of educational work are a requirement of the time. Education is, first of all, the process of assimilating social norms of behavior through the interaction of people with each other. “Human relations are the mutual movement of a subject and an object, which has a directional character. The attitude is only human and fair only in the bosom of society. In this sense, the aesthetic processing of reality is a special type of interaction between subject and object. To identify and perceive the features of an aesthetic attitude means to reveal and perceive the nature of its subject and mutual actions” [6, 79].

In conditions of independence, interpersonal relationships acquire a completely new meaning and acquire a moral and humane character. In such conditions, education becomes one of the main tasks of the entire society. Since the upbringing of young people is so important, since high human qualities are instilled in them through upbringing, the teacher needs to be well aware of the internal and external mechanisms of influence on them. To do this, first of all, it is necessary to know the object of education that is being influenced, that is, the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the student’s personality.

Man comes into the world as a biological species. However, the fact that it is a biological breed does not fully express its essence. His essence is a social being, and the social factor is important for the formation of a person as an individual. Man as a complex subjective system is formed and develops under the influence of social and biological characteristics. These two characteristics are interrelated in the formation of personality and influence internal and external factors. Speaking about human education, it is necessary to take into account internal (biological) and external environmental factors of education, as well as controlled and not always controlled influences. Taking these factors into account, each secondary school must create its own system for educating students. Its purpose, content, principles, form and methods should prepare the ground for the development of the student’s personal qualities and deep mastery of the chosen specialty. Such a system of educational work should be built on the basis of certain requirements and principles. For example, the principle of continuity—building on and continuing previous traditions—encourages students to stick together and take initiative.

Compliance with a certain sequence, regularity in educational work, ensuring its smoothness, consistent logic, regime, avoiding interruptions, random events, taking into account the age characteristics of students leads to the complication of the content of the form and methods of educational work. The education of students in secondary schools is based on continuous organization, regularity of work over time, the mutual

exchange of tensions and contractions during the school year and puts an end to spontaneity, company, and violent behavior.

The content of the system of educational work carried out with students is divided into components of education - spiritual, patriotic and international, moral, ideological, political, legal, labor, physical, aesthetic, religious, environmental, hygienic, economic, various types of student learning activities - individual, collective, includes the participation of class leaders and school leaders in collective, public general forms. Its content is realized through various forms and methods [8].

However, observations and surveys show that not all people actually engaged in educational work have a clear idea about it. Some understand the system as a sequence of work, others as a periodic repetition of events, and still others as a complex line of activity. The emerging diversity has a negative impact on the organization of the educational process. This is due to the fact that students do not have a holistic understanding of the educational process, and in most cases, due to the lack of desire to read scientific and methodological literature and receive up-to-date information, teachers do not rise to the level of understanding the integrity of the entire system by working with individual, unrelated, isolated parts, directions and elements. Second, even if a system is organized on this basis, it can be very error-prone, correction-oriented, and time-consuming. However, knowledge of the scientific foundations of the educational process can guarantee that the system will work with high efficiency and achieve high results without errors and stress [7].

Observations made it possible to identify a number of typical shortcomings in the organization of educational work. For example, a common shortcoming is that educational content is incomplete. As a result of this, not being able to clearly imagine the initial state of the system, teachers are unable to distinguish between form and content and replace planning with the distribution of forms in time and place. As a result, some component falls out of the system. That is why the teacher must clearly define the purpose and content of his work. The form is chosen according to the content; the form is not determining, but driven. The inability to correctly set a goal negatively affects the formation of a student's personality and the formation of a mature personality. Paying attention to the form and their quantity when organizing educational work reduces students' interest in it and causes indifference. Only on this basis will it be possible to ensure the professional maturity of future specialists who have moral maturity, integrity of human, personal and moral qualities. Solving this problem on a scientific and pedagogical basis requires knowledge of the laws and principles of the educational process.

One of the characteristic shortcomings in the organization of educational work for students in secondary schools is the inability to determine its ideological, political, and

moral orientation. Some teachers, not realizing the unity and interdependence of its directions in the educational process, understand that spiritual and moral education is solved only through weekly collective dialogues and conversations. In order for the educational work of students to be effective and efficient, it largely depends on ideology and morality, which are its defining criteria.

This activity will be highly effective if, in the educational work of students in general education schools, pedagogical leadership, initiative, independence and self-organization, and self-education are carried out as an integral system.

REFERENCES:

1. Karimov I.A. We build our future with our own hands. Speech at the closing meeting of the 155th session of the UNESCO Executive Board. Volume 7. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", - 1999. 39 p.
2. Karimov I.A. We build our future with our own hands. Answers to questions from a correspondent of the newspaper "Turkiston". - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", -1999. - 31 s.
- 3 Karimov I.A. Basic principles of the political, social and economic perspective of Uzbekistan // The Motherland is sacred, like a shrine. Volume 3. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", - 1996. -5 p.
4. Karimov I.A. Independence and spirituality. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan". - 1994. - 160 rub. Page 13.
5. Karimov I.A. National independent economy, politics, ideology of Uzbekistan. / Works Volume 1. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", -1996. Page 31.
6. Jami A. To my child. - Tashkent: - 1977. P. 79.
7. G. Zaripova, A. I. Hikmatov, O.K.Temiro, D.B.Salimova. IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM, UPGRADING AND RETRAINING OF PEDAGOGIC PERSONNEL IS THE CURRENT DEMAND. // «ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal». ISSN: 2249-7137. Vol. 12, Issue 06, June 2022 SJIF 2022 = 8.252. A peer reviewed journal. – Page. 8. http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/7954/5040
8. G. Zaripova, A. I. Hikmatov. EDUCATION OF YOUTH IN CONDITIONS OF NATIONAL INDEPENDENCE USING THE WORKS OF OUR GREAT SCIENTISTS // «Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research». ISSN: 2278-4853. Vol. 11, Issue 6, June 2022 SJIF 2022 = 8.179. 38-44-page. http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/7955